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March 29th, 2019.

Contemporary diagnostic principles
in dentistry I

March 30th, 2019.

Contemporary diagnostic principles
in dentistry II

Novi Sad, Republic of Serbia

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On behalf of the Scientific Committee, I'm pleased to welcome you at the Forth International Scientific Conference in Dentistry 2019 Novi Sad.

I had the great privilege and pleasure of being among the organization team in the past meetings and the President of Scientific Committee of the current one in 2019.

The Scientific and Organization Committee have made every effort to plan a conference that is scientifically satisfactory and socially interesting.

You will meet with an exceptional program covering different topics, from basic research areas to areas within daily practice of Restorative Dentistry, Endodontics, Prosthodontics, Oral Surgery and Implantology, Periodontology, Paediatric and Preventive Dentistry. Technical and Dental Material exhibits will also form an important segment of the Conference.

Apart from the scientific aspect of the Conference we wish you to experience the traditional hospitality of Novi Sad and to strengthen the existing friendships and create a lot of new ones.

*President of the Scientific Committee
Dr Milica Jeremić Knežević, assistant professor*

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INTRAORAL SCANNERS-DIGITAL IMPRESSION

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Abstract: Devices for taking direct optical impressions in dentistry which are based on creating a digital three-dimensional tooth virtual model in a quick and easy way, are intraoral scanners (IOS). The informations that digital models can provide at the beginning of treatment are inviolate and leads to much better diagnoses and even better quality of treatments. However, as IOS have been recently introduced commercially, they are not used frequently in everyday clinical practice. IOS that are current present onto the market are sufficiently accurate for capturing impressions in fabricating every prosthetic restoration and they are most often used for these purposes.

Key words: scanners, intraoral scanners, digital impression, optical impression

Introduction

Medical and dental practice undergone significant improvements with introduction of 3D (three-dimensional) technology for the purpose of diagnosis and treatment of the patients. So called digital impressions using IOS is the first step in “digital flow” proceeding of prosthodontic treatment.

Intraoral scanners (IOS) are devices for capturing direct optical impressions in dentistry [1–3]. As other three-dimensional scanners, they use a light source (laser or structured light) directing it onto the object to be captured. In dentistry objects usually are upper or lower dental arch, prepared teeth or implant scanbodies (transfers) [3, 4]. IOS come in several types, sizes and formates, which allows the recording of almost every part of the oral cavity. Some intraoral scanners are adapted for recording the frontal teeth, some for lateral teeth, and there are also those intended for use specially for children and specially for adults. Some of them have curved ending of the probe which makes easier recording the oral cavity from all angles, especially molars - Figure 1 (a, b, c, d).

Fig. 1. Types of intraoral scanners: a) iTero; b) 3Shape; c) 3M Espe; d) Cerec

The scanning process

Improved workflow results in a continuous process from the moment the shot was taken with an intraoral scanner. Mostly, it significantly reduces the time required to produce prints until delivery of the application, saves the time of doctors and patients. Digital workflow process, in contrast to the traditional one, has several steps less. After digital impression comes appliance design, then 3D (three-dimensional) printing process and appliance delivery at the end. This implies that the communication between a dentist and dental technician is quick and simple and enables cooperation that saves time as well as resources - Figure 2.

Fig. 2. Digital workflow process

The 3D surface models of the dento-gingival tissues are the result of the optical impression and are the 'virtual' alternative to traditional plaster models [5, 6]. IOS are devices which are comprised of a manual camera (hardware), computer, and software. The aim of IOS is to capture with precision the three-dimensional geometry of an object. The images captured in oral cavity by imaging sensors are processed by the scanning software, which generates point clouds [4, 5]. The most widely used digital format is the open STL (Standard Tessellation Language) or locked STL - Figure 3(a). This format describes a succession of triangulated surfaces where each triangle is defined by three points and a normal surface. These point clouds are then triangulated by the same software, creating a 3D surface model (mesh) [4-6]. It is recommended that files are stored in open format. The reason for this is that each laboratory uses a different format. No matter what type of imaging technology IOS uses, all cameras require the projection of light that is then recorded as individual images or video and compose by the software after recognition of the POI (points of interest). The first two coordinates (x and y) of each point are evaluated on the image, and the third coordinate (z) is then calculated depending on the distance to object technologies of each camera - Figure 3(b) [6]. The main characteristic an IOS should have is an accuracy [1-9]. In metrics and engineering, accuracy is defined as the 'closeness of agreement between a measured quantity value and a true quantity value of a measurand', so the sum of trueness and precision is the accuracy and when the accuracy of IOS are testing both of characteristics are evaluating [4-9].

Fig. 3. Creation of a STL file by an intraoral camera: a) STL file; b) scheme of calculation the third coordinate and generation 3D projection of virtual model

There are many dental tissues that can present reflective surfaces (enamel crystals or polished surfaces) that could disrupt the matching of POI by the software due to overexposure. To prevent this, clinicians can change the orientation of the camera to increase diffuse light, or use cameras with a polarizing filter [10]. For some scanners, a 20–40 μm powder coating is required during the digitizing process to decrease reflectivity. The powder thickness could vary between operators and reduce file accuracy, but the software of the IOS is capable of calculating an average thickness into the measurement [11].

Advantages and disadvantages of optical impressions

The classic conventional impressions can often cause discomfort for the patient with strong gag reflex, or children due to the inconvenience and hardship stemming from the materials positioned in fabricated or special impression trays. Impression made by IOS decreases patient discomfort and eliminates the need for materials and impression trays and patient usually prefer digital scanning process compared to the traditional one [12]. Digital impression allows the skipping of an inescapable phase in conventional impression technique as making of physical impressions and casting of gypsum models with a huge time-saving effect. It translates into direct savings for the clinician and technician, with reduced consumables costs [3, 5, 7]. After performing the scan, the dentist can instantly e-mail it to the laboratory, the technician checks it and if not satisfied clinician can make another one without any loss of time. Patients usually feel more involved with optical impressions in their treatment and it is the easier way to achieve better communication with them as well as with technicians [3, 7]. The most frequent problems related with optical impressions is difficulty in detecting deep marginal lines on prepared teeth or scanning intraoral tissues in the case of bleeding. There is a learning curve for adopting IOS in the dental clinic, and this aspect must be considered with attention. Younger dentist with a greater affinity for the technological improvements and computers will easier accept IOS in their practice, but older one with less experience and passion for digital innovations could find using the devices and related software more complicated [13, 14]. Like any other technological innovation, intraoral scanners and extra equipment have a high price and these devices are not very widespread in dental offices [2-4]. In the current literature most scientists considers the accuracy of optical impressions clinically satisfactory and similar but not better than conventional impressions in the case of single-tooth restoration and fixed partial prostheses of up to 4–5 elements [1, 4–9, 11] (Table 1.).

Table 1. Advantages and disadvantages of intraoral scanners (digital impressions)

Advantages	Disadvantages
more comfort for patient	hard to detect deep margin lines bleeding barrier
saving time and resources	learning curve
simpler procedure	Cost
better communication between dentist, technicians and patients	same accuracy as conventional impression

Conclusion

Digital impression and digital process of dental restoration relative to conventional methods has many advantages and the most important one is that it is always the same regardless of the patient, while using the conventional methods this process varies and depends of many factors. Advantages as saving time and materials are evident, and simplification of the procedure and excellent communication between the practitioner and patient as well as between clinician and technician are irreplaceable. Regarding to the prices of models obtained by conventional methods, the price varies and can be very high if the dentist has to make impression several times. With digital impressions, this is not the case because the technician can consult a dentist immediately after the first results and point out possible mistakes while the patient is still in the chair. Still, IOS also have disadvantages such as indications that are limited to small prosthetic restorations due to lower accuracy when it comes to big restorations and inaccessibility to certain details especially when the bleeding factor is present. The IOS currently available at the market vary in terms of accuracy, therefore, the latest-generation devices have wider indications for clinical use and they can not only be used in fixed prosthodontics to obtain the virtual models needed to manufacture a whole range of prosthetic restorations on natural teeth and implants, but also in implantology for guided surgery and in orthodontics. Inventioning an intraoral scanner of great precision and accuracy that would expose its indications to many dental branches would much facilitate further clinical practice, and considering the growth and development of technology it's possible and near.

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